

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CATERING SERVICES IN TOURISM AND HOTELS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and practical basis of the normative assessment of consumer requirements for improving the quality of accommodation and general catering services for the population in tourism and hotels has been researched.

Forecasts of medium-term multi-variant scenarios of the development of the system of tourism and accommodation and general catering services for the population of Kashkadarya region have been developed based on a complex number of empirical models.

Creating favorable economic and organizational-legal conditions for the rapid development of tourism as a strategic branch of the country's economy, more fully and effectively using the huge tourism potential of the regions, fundamentally improving the management of the tourism network, creating national tourism products and promoting them in the world markets, and promoting Uzbekistan in the field of tourism In order to form a positive image, extensive scientific researches are being conducted aimed at the organization and innovative development of high-quality catering services in tourism and hotels.

As part of the ongoing scientific research, it is important to ensure the safety of life and health of tourists and excursionists in the organization of tourism services, first of all, in the places where tourists are accommodated, in eating places, when moving around the territory of the republic, when organizing visits to tourism objects.

In the countries of the world, tourism is one of the promising directions that determine the strategic development of countries, individual regions and regions. According to the 2021 report of the UNWTO "World Tourism

Barometer", "a slowdown in international tourism could lead to a loss of US\$ 1.3 trillion in export earnings in the sector, which is eleven times more than the losses recorded during the global economic crisis of 2009".[5] however, tourism remains an important development factor throughout the world. In addition to the historical-cultural, natural-climatic, geographic-ecological attractiveness of a specific region or country, the level of attraction of the tourist flow is determined by the level of political goodwill, the potential of specialists, the appropriate infrastructure and the level of quality of various services. Therefore,

Also, tourism, as the most priority sector in providing employment, has become one of the criteria for economic stability.¹ At the moment, this network is considered as the most important tool for increasing the tourism potential of countries². The worldIn assessing the quality of life of the population, great attention is paid to the increase in the share of their consumption of food products in public catering establishments, and the level of housing provision. In developed foreign countries, more than 50 percent of food products are consumed in catering establishments. Globally though this indicator is around 8 percent and remains very low [7]. According to the data of the German international statistics company (Statista), the size of the hotel and resort industry market worldwide grew until 2020, and has significantly decreased during the COVID-19 pandemic. Global hotel revenue decreased by 46% to \$198.6 billion in 2020. At the same time, the industry is predicted to grow to 950 billion dollars in 2021, but in practice this figure has not been reached.³According to the information of the international hotel statistics organization (Hoteltechreport), the full recovery may not take place even in 2023.⁴Although the development of the accommodation and public catering network is associated with the increase in the quality of life of the country's population, and has risen to the level of an important criterion for its evaluation, in many countries, problems related to factors such as resources, infrastructure, and investment attractiveness are causing a decrease in the level of development of the sector.

In the theoretical basis of the development of the field of accommodation and general catering services, this type of models acquires the character of development. The use of Type 1 models in field development theory is often overlooked. The main reason for this is the social reality of the network of accommodation and catering services, which is directly related to the inner

¹Electronic resource:<https://natural-sciences.ru/ru/article/view?id=12967>

²Electronic resource:https://elibrary.worldbank.org/doi/pdf/10.1596/9780821394656_CH09

³Electronic resource:<https://www.statista.com/topics/1102/hotels/#dossierKeyfigures>

⁴Electronic resource:<https://hoteltechreport.com/news/hospitality-statistics>

psyche of a person.

For example, in the United States, which is the leading country in terms of GDP, the annual market size of accommodation and catering services in 2021 will grow by 24.7% compared to 2020 and will reach 853,143.4 million dollars, the average growth rate for 2016-2021 is 98.2 which is equal to percent⁵. Even if tourism and other entertainment services are taken into account, its average share in GDP does not exceed 4 percent. Also, the accommodation and catering services market in Vietnam, which has moved from poverty to middle-income countries, is forecast to generate revenues of \$28.4 billion in 2021, with an average growth rate of more than 19 percent over the next 10-15 years.⁶ In other words, in most of the countries that are in the process of economic development, a high growth rate is observed in the network of accommodation and catering services. The same opinions are presented in the conclusions based on scientific analysis of several foreign researchers [8]. In our opinion, although the level of development is not high, the countries where this process is accelerating, first of all, were able to correctly assess the factors of development and made the right choice. Then, in accordance with the above information, opinions and conclusions, among these factors, the development of accommodation and catering services is also very important.

The psychological SOR (stimulus-organism-response) model[9] of professors L. Goa and X. Bai of the Australian University of Tasmania is widely used by researchers in the development of the service network of the economy. In this, the main essence is the achievement of effective results of the mental system related to the satisfaction of consumer needs and supplier interests. The model is a theoretical object of forming a model marketing system in the field of services.

The TAM (technology acceptance model) model[10] of Professor F. Davis of the University of Michigan is a theory of technology acceptance and is used to model how users accept technology and its effective use. Classic models like these are playing a key role in shaping the modern theory of residential and catering service network development today. For example, the Chinese economist Sh.F. Chou in his studies related to the construction of sustainable marketing principles in catering, determining the important factors of ensuring the effectiveness of marketing innovations in the catering services market [11] combined the SOR and TAM models into the SEM (structural equation) of

⁵Electronic resource:<https://www.ibisworld.com/industry-statistics/market-size/accommodation-food-services-united-states/>

⁶Electronic resource:<https://kun.uz/50300510?q=%2F50300510>

marketing management of catering services modeling) develops a model.

Development models that structurally parametrically express a new view of a specific object-oriented, integrated system, or its independent system, include the agromarket parametric model of K. Umachandrat, a researcher of the Indian multidisciplinary engineering management development organization.⁷, J.R. Bolt's Semiparametric and Parametric Classification Model for Direct Services Marketing⁸, A. Khutoretskyi and N. Nefedkin's two-parameter game theory model of service concession [12] and others. Models like this have been serving as a theoretical basis for the formation of the innovative marketing system of economic sectors, including the service network.

In the process of our research, we used the principle of the factor approach to determine the priority directions for the development of the residential and catering network for the population.

There is a special recognition of methodological scientists about the importance of the factor approach principle in modeling the management and development of economic and social systems. According to I. D. Voronina and E. A. Egorov, "the factor approach is the most effective method of researching a holistic system, the object of which is a social system that does not have an objective numerical expression" [13]. According to S. Limarie and S. Maretti, "the factor approach is a principle that creates a wide opportunity for a comprehensive analysis of the socio-economic process" [14].

Foreign economists Sh. Aixua, Sh. Yunshua, F. Xiao, Sh. Haiong, D. In the researches of Hengnian, G. Prayang, M. Landre, S. Ryan [15], the obvious influence of urban planning infrastructure on the development of this economic network in countries with different levels of development is justified against the background of the issue of spatial distribution of hotels and catering facilities.

In the scientific works of R. Verdichcha, P. Lago, K. Vries, M. Slot, M. Frakin, R. Damgrou, E. Lutters [16] digital infrastructure is evaluated as the main factor that creates many development factors in the future. Even in the service sector, they note that the rise of digital transformation is inevitable. B. Urban, L. Matela, B. Bredemier, S. Hermann, K. Sattler, K. Prager, J. Rex [17] as a result of scientific researches in the field of modern services, in the organization of services in relation to factors such as competition, price, assortment of goods, service it is concluded that it occurs with a high level of innovative development.

⁷Electronic resource: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270393180_Parametric_Model_in_Agriculture_Marketing_-_Module_2; https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270281397_Parametric_Models_in_Agricultural_Marketing_-_Module_1

⁸Electronic resource: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/002224379303000309?journalCode=mrja>

In the scientific works of S.A. Denisov, A.A. Sorokin, M. Sukhari, M. Dressel, S. Schuch-Zoller [18] and other foreign scientists, the importance of scientific-theoretical foundations in the development of practice in the service sector has been extensively covered. Also, in the opinion of S.A. Denisov, the field of services that is not based on any scientific research cannot exist, and as long as digital platforms and the online service system do not work, its future is zero.

In the studies carried out, the factor approach is limited to focusing on a set of factors characterized by a certain selected development direction. The reason for this is the convenience of setting the priority directions specific to the type of development with the scientific bases that ensure the priority of the factors related to this set. Nevertheless, the development of the field has a synergistic character, and we believe that it is appropriate that the research process here chooses only the direction of improvement, without denying all the successful episodes of the previous, current periods. In this sense, the most optimal solution for the selection of factors in the process of our research is the formation of synergy of the influence of factors that have the status of priority in different directions of development. Provardi can create a set of synergistic factors. According to scientists,⁹. Also, all the variables of the development of the industry in real-time mode or in social reality, which cover the uncertain, sufficiently complex nature of the economic processes, are prone to nonlinearity, and are not balanced. In our opinion, a set of internal and external factors related to the whole system, whose level and quantitative measure changes while maintaining the impact characteristic in a dynamic process, is a set of synergistic factors of econometric research.

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⁹Electronic resource:<https://lib.usue.ru/resource/free/12/s69.pdf>// Kuznetsov B.L. Teoriya synergeticheskogo razvitiya ekonomicheskikh sistem: Nab. Chelny : Izd-vo Kam. Mr. Eng.-Econ. Acad., 2010.

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In the systematic research of a set of synergistic factors, which is considered as the identification of priority factors, the most effective are the network analysis according to the network symbol, as well as the perspective and retrospective analyzes differentiated according to the time symbol.

To ensure the sustainable development of accommodation and catering services, the efficiency of resource use, to have optimal solutions using econometric methods in the development and organization of management, to ensure food security of the population based on the development of future forecast indicators of the industry, to increase the level of employment, to stimulate tourism special importance is given to research works. In the conditions of today's innovative development based on the principle of digitization of tourism service networks, attention is paid to the introduction of new methods and innovative technologies to the accommodation and public catering network, and the identification of priority directions of development based on the optimal use of the existing territorial economic potential.

A number of reforms and practical measures are being implemented to establish the new Uzbekistan as an economically stable country. In particular, in order to improve the quality of life of the population, a special priority is given to the development of accommodation and catering services. In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, "creating an infrastructure conducive to the development of the tourism services sector, encouraging specialized entrepreneurship, increasing employment in the sector, launching new hotels and catering establishments in order to increase the tourism potential of our country, and improving the mechanisms for improving the quality of service"[10], a number of priority tasks have been defined. To ensure the performance of these tasks, modern research methods of accommodation and catering,

No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", dated

October 5, 2020 "On approval of the Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and measures for its effective implementation Decree No. PF-6079, Decision No. PQ-5232 of August 25, 2021 "Additional measures to support the catering and tourism sectors"¹⁰, and this article serves to a certain extent in the implementation of tasks defined in other regulatory legal documents related to the field.

In the organization of regional tourism activities, the implementation of technological innovations in hotels and restaurants where tourists are accommodated, the formation of appropriate infrastructure and the establishment of high-quality catering services, the spatial differentiation of the eco-efficiency of regional tourism, the escalation of environmental problems and the level of air pollution above the standard safety level set by the World Health Organization 2 Environmentally responsible ecotourism, which is increasing 5 times (its share in the world market of tourism services is 181.1 billion US dollars per year, the annual growth rate is 14.3 percent)¹¹making the development of 1 out of every 8 deaths (oncological diseases, respiratory system diseases, birth defects in babies) caused by atmospheric pollution and the use of toxic chemicals are caused by environmental diseases.¹². The most effective economic strategy to prevent environmental pollution is the development of ecotourism in potential areas.

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¹⁰www.lex.uz / National database of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan

¹¹<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1221034/ecotourism-market-size-global/#statisticContainer>

¹²World Health Statistics 2018. <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/272596/9789241565585-eng.pdf>

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